

The role of energy recovery from wastes in the decarbonization efforts of the EU power sector

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Abstract

Wastes contain large quantities of energy that can be extracted using a variety of methods. European Union has established a waste-to-energy initiative to minimize waste and increase recovery. The EU Landfill Directive promotes more environmental friendly waste management options. Accordingly, EU member states are adopting mechanical-biological treatment processes, bio-methanization and waste-derived fuels. Furthermore, EU is energy-dependent, as its resources are insufficient to meet rising energy demands, and fossil fuels must be imported in large quantities. Wastes are increasingly produced and have a non-negligible lower calorific value that are considered as a power source. Findings highlight the role of waste-to-energy facilities in meeting a portion of the European Union's energy needs and contributing to the achievement of renewable energy targets. The untapped potential, through specific actions, can increase capacity in EU without threatening the goals for recycling. This work presents the current status of energy recovery in EU and investigates the unutilized potential energy recovery from wastes, considering the currently landfilled quantities. The results showed that even in the worst scenario, the energy recovery and the renewable content are too high to be neglected, supporting the decarbonization efforts and enhance circular economy, in line with EU's Energy Strategy and Paris agreement.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Over the last few years, global energy demand has risen, and this trend is expected to continue. Almost all European Union (EU) countries are suffering from a shortage of energy services. Annually, EU fossil fuel energy production falls; for example, in 2014, gas production fell by 11.2% compared to 2013 [1]. Energy imports, especially natural gas, have increased as a result of lower energy output. The EU is still heavily reliant on fossil fuel imports (oil and gas), and the cost of EU energy imports in 2017 increased by 26% (€266 billion) [2]. The

primary major threat to the EU's energy security is energy dependency. One of the EU's strategies to address the problem is to increase endogenous output, specifically renewable energy [1]. Because of the EU's energy dependence and strong efforts to minimize environmental impact and mitigate climate change, the EU has set clear, aggressive goals for reducing pollution in the power sector and becoming carbon neutral. In order to achieve this goal, the EU is turning to renewable energy sources and gradually shutting down fossil power plants, with gas-fired power plants and nuclear power plants serving as transition fuels before 100% renewable energy is achieved [3–5]. The EU is also

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emphasizing the importance of a multifaceted approach to meet citizens' electricity and heat demand needs, with an emphasis on renewable energy sources that can supply both if possible [1, 2, 4, 6].

At the same time, the EU is attempting to create a circular economy and convert all wastes into energy by taking a multifaceted approach that emphasizes prevention, reuse, and recycling as the most beneficial methods. Of course, energy recovery is beneficial, and it can be accomplished in a variety of ways, including waste-to-energy (WTE) and anaerobic digestion (AD). This may convert large quantities of waste into electricity, heat, or biogas for pipe outputs [7–10]. These energy recovery methods are either 100% renewable, such as biogas, or partly renewable, with 50–80% renewable material, depending on the waste composition [7–13]. The EU has developed policies to boost the development of renewable energy resources, such as Waste-to-Energy plants, and to achieve a more balanced energy policy [1]. The growing amount and complexity of municipal solid waste (MSW) created by households and, to a lesser extent, small businesses and public buildings such as schools and hospitals, is posing a serious threat to the environment and human health [3]. Owing to the space requirements and pollution, waste landfilling is only done in part. Waste management policies in the EU are intended to reduce waste's environmental and health impacts while also increasing resource recovery. These policies have a long-term aim of reducing waste production and, in cases where waste generation is inevitable, promoting wastes as a resource [4]. In 2016, the EU generated 5 tonnes of waste per capita, with a total waste production of 2538 million tonnes in the EU-28 from all economic activities and households [4]. MSWs account for around 10% of total waste produced in Europe. According to the European Environment Agency (EEA), 481 kg of MSW was generated per person in the 33 member countries in 2012. Since 2007, there has been a slight downward trend, which could be explained in part by the European economic crisis that began in 2008 [5].

Across the EU, more waste is being recycled and less is being disposed of in landfills. In the case of MSWs, the proportion of recycled or composted waste increased from 31% in 2004 to 41% in 2012 in the 27 EU countries [5]. There are, however, significant differences between countries. The produced MSW has a non-negligible lower calorific value, making it a viable power source [6]. This is a strong possibility [7], given the EU's current approach to resource efficiency and its deep experience with WTE facilities. According to a report published by the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in 2011, only 12% of MSW produced in 2010 was converted to energy through WTE operations, with the remaining 54% being landfilled [8]. Instead of landfilling, energy production from MSW generates less methane gas, which is 25 times the mass of CO₂, and reduces fossil fuel imports [9, 10]. Landfilling MSW is a massive waste of valuable resources and energy, as well as a missed opportunity to create new jobs, boost economic growth, and minimize waste's negative effects [11]. European countries adopt waste management approaches that include separation at the source and mechanical-biological treatment (MBT)

processes as a result of the EU Landfill Directive (1999/31 EC) [11]. MBT is a well-known MSW treatment method. If anaerobic digesters are used, MBT processes produce many production sources, including compost-like digested content, a high calorific value fuel stream (1518 MJ/kg), metals, residuals, and biogas [12]. Plastic, paper, textiles, and wood make up the majority of the high calorific value fuel stream. Depending on the characteristics of the waste-derived fuel from MSW, it is referred to as refuse-derived fuel (RDF) or solid recovered fuel (SRF) [13]. The current state of energy recovery from wastes is assessed in this paper in light of the EU's energy transition efforts, with an emphasis on its contribution to the power sector. The aim of this paper is to assess the potential function and significance of WTE facilities, SRF/RDF usage, and AD infrastructure in meeting a portion of the EU's electricity and heat demand, excluding the provision of a complete solution for non-recyclable waste treatment. The results of this evaluation show that the role of wastes as a source for energy can have a role that cannot be neglected. In addition, this work tries to evaluate the untapped potential of WTE in EU based on the most recent data and attempts to calculate the potential energy recovery (renewable and non-renewable one) accordingly, using approaches that are based on successful implementations that will not threaten the efforts for increased recycling, in contrast to other related approaches [14], where this potential is evaluated through different thinking. This evaluation also shows that there is significant potential that can be utilized, especially in the countries that now are depending mainly on coal and lignite for power production, thus the adoption of WTE will result in a notable contribution in the efforts of decarbonizing the EU power sector.

2 | EU POWER SECTOR

In 2017, primary energy output in the EU-28 was 758 million tonnes of oil equivalent (toe), a decrease from previous years. Primary energy output in the EU-28 was 17.3% lower in 2014 than it was in 2004 over the long term. In 2017, France had the largest share of primary energy output (17.4%) among the EU-28 countries, led by the United Kingdom (15.6%) and Germany (15.3%). In absolute terms, 17 of the EU's 27 countries saw an increase in primary energy output from 2007 to 2017. Italy had the highest increase in production (5.5 Mtoe), followed by Spain with 4.1 Mtoe, Sweden with 3.7 Mtoe, Ireland with 3.4 Mtoe, and Finland with 2.0 Mtoe. However, primary energy output fell to 57.6 Mtoe in the United Kingdom, with contractions of more than 10 Mtoe in Germany (−20.6 Mtoe), the Netherlands (−18.5 Mtoe), and Denmark (−11.3 Mtoe) [1, 11].

In 2017, primary energy production in the EU-28 was rendered by a variety of energy sources, the most important of which, in terms of contribution, were renewable energy sources (RES), which accounted for 29.9% of total production, followed by nuclear energy, which accounted for 27.8%. Nuclear energy accounted for nearly 79% of France's primary energy output, while it accounted for nearly 75% in Belgium and 62.6% in Slovakia. Nuclear energy accounted for less than half of primary

Production of primary energy, EU-28, 2017
(% of total, based on tonnes of oil equivalent)

FIGURE 1 Production of primary energy, EU-28, 2017 (% of total, based on toe), with a breakdown of the renewable production shares (Source and copyright: Eurostat)

production in 11 other nations, and there was no nuclear energy production in 14 EU members. Strong fossil fuels (16.4%, mostly coal) had a share of just under one quarter, natural gas (13.6%), and crude oil (8.8%) were the only other major sources of primary energy output (Figure 1) [1].

According to the 2030 climate and energy framework, the EU's key goals and policy priorities for the period 2021 to 2030 are: (a) a 40% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels), (b) a 32% share for renewable energy, and (c) a 32.5% increase in energy efficiency [3, 4, 14, 16, 17]. These goals will include the basis for the EU to meet the Paris Agreement's goals and combat climate change by limiting global warming to 1.5 °C [3, 4, 10, 14, 16, 17].

Improvements in energy efficiency have many benefits, including cost reductions, air pollution control, and greenhouse gas emission reduction, as well as improved human health, energy savings, and energy stability. Combining energy recovery efficiency and technical methods will result in low-carbon cities [2, 3, 4, 10, 16, 17].

3 | WASTE PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT IN THE EU

Waste, described in Article 3 (1) of EU Directive 2008/98 / EC as "any substance or object which the holder discards, intends, or is needed to discard", represents a potentially massive loss of resources, both in terms of materials and energy [7]. Furthermore, waste treatment and disposal may have significant environmental consequences. Landfills, for example, occupy land and can pollute the air, water, and soil, while incineration can pollute the air. Waste management policies in the EU are intended to reduce environmental and health impacts of wastes while also increasing resource production. The long-term aim of these policies is to minimize waste production and, if waste

production is inevitable, to encourage waste as a resource and increase recycling and waste disposal safety [7–10, 14, 15, 18–26]. As the European society has become wealthier, more MSW has been developed. In the EU, 3 billion tonnes of waste are discarded per year. In 2018, the EU provided 489 kg of municipal waste per capita. Managing such amounts without causing environmental damage becomes a major concern for all EU member states [11, 12], many of which have so far struggled to implement waste management techniques [8–10, 14, 18–26].

Between 2000 and 2010, the amount of waste generated in the EU increased by 10%, with the majority of it being thrown away, burned in incinerators, or discarded in landfill sites (67%). Landfilling consumes precious land space while also polluting the air, water, and soil by releasing CO₂ and CH₄ into the atmosphere as well as contaminants into groundwater and soil [9, 10]. Despite the EU's policy of preventing biodegradable waste from ending up in landfills, landfilling remains the most common disposal method in Europe, accounting for roughly half of the 243 million tonnes of MSW produced annually in the EU's 28 member states (EU-28). WTE facilities in Europe now handle 50 million tonnes of waste per year, providing enough energy to power 27 million people or provide heat for 13 million. Future amendments to EU regulations would have a major effect on environmental mitigation technologies [10].

Up until recent years, MSW was treated without energy recovery, but the consistent implementation of various EU strategies in waste management, renewable energy and energy efficiency was the reason for development of the WTE. The Directive regarding promotion of electricity generation from renewable sources (2001/77 / EC) was radical, by recognizing that the biodegradable fraction of household waste is an integral part of renewable energy as a component of biomass. It is very important to mention that these fuels are partly considered being renewable energy, depending on their composition, with each EU country setting its own percentage. [8–12, 14, 18–21, 26]

Other directives, such as the Waste Incineration Directives (2000/76 / EC) and the Industrial Emissions Guideline (2010/75/EU), also promoted the development of waste-generation facilities, resulting in lower pollutant emissions. Furthermore, the landfill directive (1999/31/ EC), which required member states to phase out biodegradable urban waste from landfills by 2016 at a rate of 35% lower than in 1995 [5, 11]. Figure 2 depicts the most recent state of waste treatment in Europe. It was created by authors using EuroStat's data [8]. This graph depicts the share of urban waste recycling (including composting), waste-to-energy, and landfilling in the EU27, including Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom, sorted by landfilling share. It also shows the data that is lacking, such as the differences between waste generated in the country and waste treated.

4 | ENERGY RECOVERY FROM WASTES

Thermal treatment (incineration), pyrolysis, gasification, mechanical biological treatment, and biological drying process

Municipal Waste Treatment in EU27 including UK, Norway and Switzerland

FIGURE 2 The state of waste treatment in EU27, Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom (data source EuroStat [8])

FIGURE 3 Possible pathways for energy recovery from wastes including most common approaches. The most common approaches, based on the number of installations/per type are indicated with green coloured letters

to generate RDF or SRF, and anaerobic digestion to create biogas are examples of WTE technologies. However, although incineration reduces waste by 95%, some is still landfilled, and pyrolysis and gasification are not yet widely used in the EU [14, 18–23]. MBT has a number of benefits, including the ability to recycle products and the reduction of landfill gas and leachate emissions. MBT systems either isolate waste before processing it or sort it before separating it [20–22, 27]. Aerobic biological unit processes are used to stabilize the organic fraction, limiting its ability to produce methane by lowering its biodegradability, while anaerobic biological unit processes aid in the production of biogas from MSW. AD has a significant benefit in terms of versatility, as it can handle a wide range of waste forms in both wet and dry environments [15, 21, 24, 25, 28, 29].

Anaerobic digestion of various forms of organic wastes, such as separately collected organic fraction of municipal wastes, agricultural and green wastes, as well as wastewater sludge and animal wastes, is an alternate route for energy recovery from wastes [9, 15, 21, 24, 25, 28]. This enables the use of wastes with high energy content to meet energy needs while also supporting initiatives toward a circular economy and the transformation of wastes into capital [9, 15, 18, 21, 24–26, 28, 29].

Biogas generated from various waste streams can provide clean electricity and heat to both urban and rural areas, as well as agricultural infrastructures and even upgraded and injected into existing natural gas networks. As a result, biogas use is critical

in microgrids and the continued growth of distributed energy sources [28, 29].

Figure 3 depicts a schematic diagram of potential energy recovery pathways from waste to power generation. The source-separated organic materials from MSW are supplied into an anaerobic digester, which produces gaseous fuels for power generation (biomethane and/or biohydrogen), while the rest of the fractions are delivered for basic mechanical and/or biological treatment, followed by power generation through various methods [11, 14, 18, 24, 30].

4.1 | Waste-to-energy in EU

WTE plants are recognized as a recovery technology capable of increasing energy efficiency by the European Cogeneration Directive (2004/8/EC), which aims to increase energy efficiency through the development of high-efficiency cogeneration. The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), adopted by the Council of Europe on the 4th of October 2012, has strengthened legislation. It encourages member states to build incineration plants that will assess the feasibility of supplying district heating and cooling networks [19].

As previously stated, each EU country decides the amount of renewable energy to be recovered from incineration plants based on the biomass content of incinerated waste (the majority

FIGURE 4 The current state of Waste-to-Energy Plants in in EU27 including Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom and the corresponding capacity of wastes used in power production either as electricity only either as CHP plants (Copyright and source CEWEP <https://www.cewep.eu/waste-to-energy-plants-in-europe-in-2018>)

applying a 50%). This amount is considered by many countries as the average energetic content of their wastes based on average composition. These values are different in Denmark and few other EU countries, where the MSW renewable content is significant higher as plastics, rubber and other non-renewable combustible materials are removed through the advance and extended source separation in waste streams [8–11, 12, 16, 18, 30]. In 2018, primary energy output from municipal waste incineration in the EU exceeded 10 Mtoe [9, 11, 14, 31, 32], if only the renewable segment is considered. The key mode of energy recovery from incinerators was still electricity. By the end of 2018, the plants had generated 3.4% more than in 2017. The United Kingdom is currently one of the most productive countries in terms of constructing new incineration plants. The United Kingdom saw the largest increase, with an additional 152.3 ktoe added for a total of 1052.8 ktoe (16.9% growth), ahead of Ireland, which saw a 46 ktoe increase in primary energy production in 2018 (49.0% more than 2017), bringing its total to 140 ktoe. France came in third place with a growth rate of 42.3 ktoe and a total production of 1326.7 ktoe (3.3%) [31]. Clearly, heat sales from these devices are far higher in countries with more common district heating systems (the Netherlands, Sweden, Germany, Denmark). According to Eurostat, in 2018, renewable (meaning the part of municipal wastes that are considered as renewable sources, for example, paper, biodegradables, wood) municipal waste treatment with energy recovery by incineration plants provided approximately 10 Mtoe of pri-

mary energy, which is similar to the previous year. Trends vary by member state, with a few countries reporting increases in renewable urban waste primary energy outputs in 2018 [8–12, 14, 31, 32].

Table 1 shows how much renewable energy the electricity only WTE and combined heat and power (CHP) WTE plants generate in EU countries. Although the quantities of energy appear to be insignificant, they are growing on an annual basis. Bear in mind, though, that this only applies to the clean energy sector. WTE plants also make a small contribution to RES electricity: 2.29% of total RES electricity in the EU [1, 8, 31, 32]. Even though such facilities exist in just a few countries, it is noteworthy. If the rest countries adopt this method, then this percentage will definitely increase significantly. Figure 4 represents the current state of WTE facilities in EU27 plus Norway, Switzerland and the UK along with the quantities of waste treated. Figure 4 was produced by CEWEP based on Eurostat's data and its reproduction is authorized, provided the source is acknowledged [11].

4.2 | RDF and SRF production and utilisation

The MBT and the biological drying process are MSW technologies for producing high calorific waste RDF or SRF depending on waste content. Metals and inerts are extracted in MBT, and

TABLE 1 Gross electricity production from renewable municipal waste in the European Union between 2005 and 2018 [1, 8, 31, 32]

Total gross electricity production in GWh from all plants					
Country	Year				
	2005	2008	2010	2014	2018
Austria	141	205	214	276	336
Belgium	326	370	591	833	968
Bulgaria	0	0	0	0	0
Croatia	0	0	0	0	0
Cyprus	0	0	0	0	0
Czech Republic	11	11	35	88	100
Denmark	998	1045	912	886	860
Estonia	0	0	0	0	46
Finland	266	295	299	441	662
France	1657	1863	1973	1971	2204
Germany	3252	4672	4747	6070	6163
Greece	0	0	0	0	0
Hungary	59	109	145	137	162
Ireland	0	0	0	72	330
Italy	1309	1556	2047	2371	2371
Latvia	0	0	0	0	0
Lithuania	0	0	0	29	48
Luxembourg	19	26	28	34	47
Malta	0	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	1266	1408	1763	1909	2172
Poland	0	0	0	0	85
Portugal	296	281	289	240	327
Romania	0	0	0	0	0
Slovakia	23	22	22	22	16
Slovenia	0	0	0	0	0
Spain	451	782	659	686	755
Sweden	524	1269	1716	1626	1656
UK	964	1240	1529	1900	3638
Total EU	11,562	15,154	16,969	19,591	22,945

organic fractions are composted, either with or without a digestion step. It also contains a high-calorie residual fraction, which is primarily made up of dry paper, plastic, and textile residues. The residual waste is dried and stabilized via a composting phase in the biological drying process (bio-drying), resulting in a residual mass with a higher calorific value, suitable for combustion. Before or after the biological drying phase, metals and inerts are extracted using a mechanical process. The schematic diagram for SRF processing is shown in Figure 5. The coarse fraction is either disposed of or reintroduced into the pulverizer's feed. Depending on where the RDF manufacturing facility is located, the medium fraction (paper, textiles, wood, and plastic) is burned and converted into coarse fuel or dried and pelletized into dense RDF [9, 13, 22, 23, 33, 34, 35].

For both RDF and SRF processing technologies, the degree of size reduction and removal of organic and inert material is critical. Due to its higher heating value, lower bulk density, and lower ash content, RDF is the most preferred fuel. However, depending on the initial waste, the composition and properties of the RDF and SRF differ [13, 22, 23, 27, 30, 33, 34]. RDF and SRF from MSW can be used and converted to energy in a variety of ways (Figure 3), including on-site in an integrated thermal conversion device, off-site at a remote facility using grate or fluidized bed combustion, co-combustion in coal-fired boilers, co-incineration in cement kilns, and co-gasification with coal or biomass [13, 17, 22, 30, 33–36]. Due to the possibility of increased pollutant emissions, co-incineration of waste in plants that were not built to incinerate waste should not be permitted. Depending to their composition RDF and SRF contain pollutants and heavy metals that are not present in lignite and coal. Power plants have to always control emissions and be equipped with adequate air pollution control (APC) systems [30, 35, 36, 37].

4.3 | Biogas production

AD is described as the bacterial decomposition of organic matter in nearly anaerobic conditions, with biogas (methanization) and digestate as by-products [9, 20, 29, 31, 38]. Thermophilic (up to 60 °C) or mesophilic (35–40 °C) conditions are used for AD. As a result, AD combined heat and electricity plants, which are now very popular in the UK (with 378 plants in 2015 [25, 29, 31, 38, 39]), are an ideal choice. The key benefit of AD is that it can handle waste with a higher moisture content (60–99%), such as food waste. Since waste is broken down to create biogas, which can be used to generate electricity, AD is a renewable energy source. Biogas can be used to produce electricity, power on-site facilities, or be converted to pure methane (biomethane) by eliminating other gases; a single m³ of biogas containing 60% methane yields 6.7 kWh of energy [25, 29, 31, 38, 39]. The UK Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) [25, 31, 38] is one example of how the former EU country is attempting to improve AD processes in order to raise financial gains from organic waste.

Biogas produced by anaerobic fermentation is classified as (a) non-hazardous waste storage facility biogas (landfill gas), (b) wastewater treatment plant sludge (sewage sludge gas), (c) methanization of non-hazardous waste or raw plant matter (other biogas), and d) biogas from thermal treatments (biogas from pyrolysis or gasification of solid biomass that produces hydrogen (H₂) and carbon monoxide (CO) [9, 21, 24, 25, 31, 38–40]). In 2018, the EU provided 62,714.4 GWh of gross electricity from all biogas plants (CHP and electricity only). Table 2 depicts overall gross electricity generation in the EU from all biogas plants, CHP, and electricity only for selected years between 2005 and 2019. Due to strict regulations for the use of food crops restricting the capacities allocated to biogas tenders and far less attractive biogas electricity remuneration conditions accounts, biogas electricity output across the EU remained constant in 2019 compared to 2018 [31, 38]. This stability in the biogas

FIGURE 5 Schematic diagram for SRF production through bio-drying [35]

electricity can be easily attribute to the reduction of the landfill biogas and the increase in AD production. As it can be seen from the EurObserv'ER's report of 2019 [31] on 'The state of renewable energies in Europe' the landfill gas was reduced from 1229.8 ktOE for EU27 in 2018 to 1177.4 ktOE for EU27 in 2019, while the total was increased. As a significant number of biogas electricity or CHP plants are actually fed from landfill gas, this reduction explains this stagnation [9, 31, 32, 38]. However, biogas production is increasing; for example, in Denmark, it increased by 27%, to 489 ktOE, in Finland, by 9%, to 186 ktOE, and in France, by 7%, to 877 ktOE [25, 31, 32, 38].

Since it can substitute petroleum-based fuels, biogas derived from MSW is a viable choice for future energy protection. By 2050, the EBA (European Biogas Association) hopes that the carbon component of the gas industry and the natural gas grid will be phased out. Biomethane ventures and alternative technologies such as biomass gasification, power to methane, and biomethane liquefaction should be prioritized by Europe's funding mechanisms, according to the EBA. The technological simplicity and storage capacities of the gas distribution grid in managing renewable electricity output, as well as the hybrid energy infrastructure based on an improved construction of gas and electricity grids, will be the solution for a decarbonized European energy system [1, 8, 21, 24, 25, 28, 29, 31, 32, 38].

5 | CURRENT STATE OF ENERGY RECOVERY FROM WASTES IN EU AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The EU has established a plan to transition from fossil fuels to renewables, with the aim of achieving a carbon-neutral energy market by 2050. The efforts also require the transition from a linear to a circular economic model. The goals are straightforward: minimize environmental damage by lowering carbon emissions in order to alleviate the effects of climate change on humans and the environment. Waste management and energy processing, often renewable, are combined in energy recovery from wastes [4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 12, 14, 19, 26, 31, 41, 42]. The statistics show that, while energy recovery from waste accounts for a small percentage of renewables and thus of the EU's electricity supply, it is not insignificant, as a large number of citizens of EU cover their needs through this approach [11, 12, 14, 19, 24, 26, 31, 32, 42].

As can be seen in Figures 6 and 7, the electricity output of such facilities is steadily growing over the last 15 years, covering higher percentages of electricity demand in the EU. The benefits of these facilities are significant because they run 24 h a day, seven days a week, and cover base load demand that is currently met by fossil or nuclear power plants. The covering

FIGURE 6 Annual evolution of the gross electricity production in GWh between 2005 and 2018 in EU from renewable municipal wastes in different types of plants [1, 8, 31, 32]

FIGURE 7 Annual evolution of the gross electricity production in GWh between 2005 and 2018 in EU from biogas in different types of plants [1, 8, 31, 32, 38]

base-load demand benefit is critical because natural gas, an intermediate fossil fuel that has been proposed as a lower-emissions fuel but is still a fossil fuel, is required to cover the base loads during the energy transition period of EU and globally [3–5, 11, 14, 15, 17, 19, 20, 22, 24, 25, 29, 31, 35, 38, 39, 42–45]. The projected rise in energy recovery from wastes would reduce emissions even further because demand for fossil and intermediate fossil fuels would be lower, bolstering the EU power sector's efforts to decarbonize [14, 19, 24–26, 29, 30, 31, 35, 41, 44].

The waste-to-energy sector has a benefit in that waste-to-energy plants are typically located near major urban centres that are both waste producers and energy users. The proximity promotes the most efficient and local use of energy, whether it is fire, electricity, or, more often than not, both, by cogeneration. Heat can also be exported more conveniently to supply a district heating network or process heat to a manufacturing facility. Since electricity users are close to the manufacturers, this has the added benefit of reducing transfer and distribution losses. In 2017, Europe had just under 500 WTE facilities in urban

TABLE 2 Total gross electricity production from all biogas facilities in the EU between 2005 and 2018 [1, 8, 25, 31, 32, 38]

Country	Year					
	2005	2008	2010	2014	2018	2019
Austria	420	601	647	618	628.3	611.9
Belgium	223	333	566	871	944.7	946.8
Bulgaria	0	0	16	62	212.3	196.9
Croatia	11	19	30	115	354.9	390.3
Cyprus	0	12	35	51	56.9	60.2
Czech Republic	160	267	635	2583	2607.2	2524.3
Denmark	281	291	357	458	613	636.2
Estonia	14	9	10	27	38	39
Finland	33	45	106	350	419.7	363.2
France	480	695	1005	1636	2369.8	2587.5
Germany	3862	12,959	17,430	31,113	33,100	32,900
Greece	122	191	190	220	316.3	377.5
Hungary	25	69	118	287	331	305
Ireland	122	176	204	203	184.1	185.3
Italy	1198	1600	2055	8198	8299.6	8276.8
Latvia	36	39	57	350	374.1	353
Lithuania	4	9	31	78	139.9	155
Luxembourg	28	44	55	61	75.5	70.9
Malta	0	0	0	7	9	6.4
Netherlands	294	734	1028	1005	886.9	894.9
Poland	111	255	398	816	1127.6	1200
Portugal	35	71	100	278	271.4	264.5
Romania	0	1	1	51	70.2	70.2
Slovakia	5	15	34	479	539	540
Slovenia	32	56	98	129	118.8	94.4
Spain	623	585	848	907	923	904
Sweden	54	30	36	14	10	17
United Kingdom	4757	5278	6059	6897	7693.4	7569.2
Total EU	12,818	24,384	32,149	57,864	62,714.4	62,540.1

areas, treating just under 100 million tonnes of renewable and non-renewable waste, according to CEWEP's latest estimates. In 2018, electricity remained the primary mode of incinerators' energy recovery [11, 12, 14, 31]. Simultaneously, statistics and literature indicate that the greener cities in the EU are those that use WTE as a recovery tool in their waste management model, in line with the renewable energy initiative and circular economy approach [10–12, 14, 18–20, 31, 32, 35, 43]. In addition to these results, the WTE strategy promotes the elimination of pollution from landfilling, the use of fossil fuels, and the utilisation of the non-recyclable waste fraction by direct mass-burning or co-firing of waste-derived fuel [11, 12, 14, 18, 19, 26, 30, 31, 35, 37, 42, 44–46], and large cities and urban areas are

choosing this approach towards zero waste [Last but not least, WtE facilities recover recyclable materials such as ferrous and non-ferrous metals from waste fractions that would otherwise be lost, while CHP plants provide heat and cooling to customers in the same cases, thus indirectly reducing carbon emissions [18–20, 35, 39, 42, 46].

The biogas sector's development has been stifled by new European regulations and decisions by the major European biogas producer countries to limit incentives and control the use of food crops. Its future growth will be driven by energy recovery from fermentable waste rather than energy crops, with thermal biogas as another growth factor. Even if the uptick in output is contingent on the adoption of a more enticing regulatory system and a more assertive political commitment to replace fossil gas, the potential for growth will remain high [21, 24, 29, 31, 38, 47].

The European Commission has already analysed the biogas sector's potential in its publication "In-depth Analysis in Support of the Commission Communication COM (2018) 73" [47]. The analyses show that methanization biogas input could increase from 16 Mtoe in 2015 to 30 Mtoe by 2030 (including a small proportion of "thermal" biogas), and according to the scenarios examined, could vary from 45 Mtoe (EE scenario) to 79 Mtoe (P2X scenario) by 2050. E-gas (biomethane produced by electrolysis) would add 91 Mtoe in 2050 according to one scenario, and between 40 and 50 Mtoe according to the other scenarios that were examined its widescale use. The EBA (European Biogas Association) points out that in order to meet the carbon neutrality target by 2050, the fossil component of the gas market and natural gas grid would have to be progressively phased out. Taxing the profits of the gas industry, along with the implementation of a European Union-wide carbon tax and the gradual elimination of fossil fuel subsidies, can logically be considered as the primary means of financing the green transition [9, 24–26, 28, 29, 31, 38]. Finally, biogas facilities are capable of generating high-quality and dense fertilizers using natural methods and recycling nutrients from biomass wastes, while CHP plants provide heat and cooling to customers in the same cases, reducing carbon emissions even further [9, 24–26, 29, 31, 28].

6 | EVALUATION OF THE POTENTIAL FOR ENERGY RECOVERY FROM WASTES IN EU AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The global community and especially EU Member States are trying hard to achieve the requested energy transition to a low or even zero carbon economy. The EU "Action Plan for a Clean Planet for All" is a clear indication that fossil energy is coming to its end [2–6, 15–17]. Low carbon societies not only require a transition in their power producing approach, but also a new approach in wastes, as waste management presents high carbon emissions today, especially with landfilling (sanitary or not) [7–11, 13, 14–20, 29, 35, 42, 46, 47]. Energy recovery from wastes presents a valuable tool and approach with proven success for many years for achieving with the same operation power generation in the form of electricity and heat and waste

management at the same time reducing the wastes volumes, recovering valuable resources and lowering carbon emissions both in waste management operations and power generation [11, 12, 14, 18, 19, 26, 29, 31, 37, 39, 41–44, 46].

Especially for EU, the issue is of high importance as many Member States are still depending on landfilling (see Figure 2) resulting in the loss of valuable products in landfills, including energy resources with a significant renewable part. At the same time these countries are the ones that depend highly on fossil fuels, such as the newest EU members, Poland, Czechia, Hungary, Romania, Malta, Cyprus, as well as older members including Greece and Portugal. From Figure 2 it is obvious that the potential for energy recovery from wastes, especially in the form of WTE is quite high. Recently, a study [14] published by the EU Joint Research Center of EU investigates the opportunities for new WTE facilities across EU-27, based on the current status. Even though this study is quite important, it does not fully investigate the actual conditions and status of the subject in each country, resulting in high number of rather small WTE speeded in each country resulting in a potential of approximately 248 new WTE in EU [14]. The problems arising from this approach can be easily identified if the findings are compared to literature. For example they propose 19 WTE plants with an average capacity of 200 kt/y in Greece where the majority of wastes are produced in 4 cities for which the related proposal exists since 2014 for only 5 plants [30, 41] and also proposing new facilities in Denmark where the Country's Strategic Plan for wastes is not to increase the capacity of the existing plants as there is adequate untapped capacity, but only to refurbished and upgrade the existing ones, without increasing capacity, targeting to increase recycling [48]. This is the main target of all EU action plans for environment and circularity, thus the assumptions in this work seems that are rather optimistic for the actual condition in each country investigated [3–5, 15–17, 47].

Considering these facts and the EU's strategic plan for a cleaner planet, the potential for waste management in the form of WTE should be considered lower than the one presented in the abovementioned paper of 2019 by N. Scarlat et al. ([14]). A more conservative approach is required as the EU countries are targeting towards recycling with increased source separation, resulting in higher potential for AD systems than WTE, which are more suitable for mixed waste streams and waste derived fuels as it has been proven in practice [9–12]. Under this approach a more reasonable even though a conservative one, should considered lower potential for WTE than the literature. An approach that the authors considering as reasonable is the reduction of the landfilling quantities in EU countries by both recycling and WTE, following the EU related legislation and the efforts for achieving a circular economy as these were presented in the EU's new circular action plan [15], with recycling as the top priority for materials recovery from wastes.

This can have many different scenarios as “potential solutions” but a more reasonable one is required, based on the fact that there are facilities in EU that do not utilize full capacity as shown in the work of Scarlat et al [14], and at the same time the fact that the complete turn from landfilling to recycling takes long time as experience have shown and the WTE is a proven

TABLE 3 Quantities of wastes in thousand tones that are going in landfilling (sanitary or dumpsite) and the incinerated ones without energy recovery (D10 category in EU waste management system) in the European Union for 2018. Data source [8]

Landfilling and Incineration without energy recovery in EU countries in thousands tonnes for 2018		
Country	Disposal— landfill and other	Disposal— incineration (D10)
EU 27	53,398	1115
Austria	113	0
Belgium	46	39
Bulgaria	1750	0
Croatia	1171	0
Cyprus	393	0
Czechia	2430	5
Denmark	53	0
Estonia	115	0
Finland	22	1
France	7342	92
Germany	410	480
Greece	4330	0
Hungary	1851	0
Ireland	418	0
Italy	6486	180
Latvia	462	0
Lithuania	320	0
Luxembourg	21	0
Malta	267	0
Netherlands	125	91
Poland	5191	191
Portugal	2518	0
Romania	4269	0
Slovakia	1248	30
Slovenia	97	7
Spain	11917	0
Sweden	30	0
Norway	124	0
United Kingdom	4613	905

technology for treating “black bags” and mixtures of biodegradable and non-degradable part of MSW as well as waste derived fuels. Table 3 presents the quantities of wastes in thousand tones that are going in landfilling (sanitary or dumpsite) and the incinerated ones without energy recovery (D10 category in EU waste management system). Figure 8 presents, three scenarios for potential change from landfilling to WTE plants, namely 30% (basic), 50% (optimistic) and 65% (very optimistic), for the EU Member States currently using landfills for over 5% of their

Scenarios for shifting from landfilling to WTE in thousands tonnes/per year

FIGURE 8 Quantities of wastes in thousand tonnes for the three scenarios evaluated and the incinerated ones without energy recovery (D10 category in EU waste management system) in selected countries of EU and UK for 2018. Data source [8]

FIGURE 9 Electricity generation potential in GWh for sifting from landfilling to WTE for the three scenarios in selected countries of EU and UK for 2018 quantities

wastes, considering the waste management options proposed in EU plans for a cleaner planet and circular economy [3–5, 15–17, 47]). For the purpose of this evaluation the Lower Heating Value of the wastes is considered to be 9 MJ/kg or 2.5 kWh/kg [30], which is the case for mixed wastes with high percentage of biodegradable and packaging wastes, most common one for the majority of the countries in the Figure 8. Figure 9 presents the potential for energy recovery in terms of electricity considering advance facilities with a 31% net (35% gross) output efficiency for electricity only plants [44], which results to an average of

775 kWh/t of waste incinerated. Figure 10 presents the respective renewable electricity potential considering 50% renewable content and 35% as a more conservative one covering all cases based on the data given in literature for the future waste stream mixes [9, 14, 30, 44, 47], in total for the selected EU countries and UK while Table 4 shows the values in each country for all scenarios.

The calculations of each scenario consider that all quantities that are incinerated without energy recovery will be forwarded to existing or new WTE plants, as this category of disposal

FIGURE 10 Electricity generation potential in GWh for sifting from landfilling to WTE for the three scenarios in selected countries of EU and UK for 2018 quantities

(D10) in EU is no-longer acceptable under the green deal and circular economy, as it can be easily concluded from the reading of these documents [3, 4, 9, 17], and these facilities must shut-down. In addition, Scarlat et al. [14] have shown in their work that in many countries the existing WTE plants are not operating in full capacity and thus there is a potential gap in waste volumes that can be directed there to have these facilities operating at their maximum capacity. In each scenario the indirect benefits are also quite interesting as the WTE facilities and the countries chosen them as one of the tools for waste management present higher recycling rates, as many published papers and reports have shown [9, 12, 17–20, 37, 46], resulting in indirect increase of energy efficiency as the materials recovered from wastes and especially metals can significantly reduce the quantities of energy required for their reprocess [9, 10, 12, 18, 35]. Additional benefits arisen is the reduction of carbon emissions not only from power generation, but also emissions that can be avoided as these wastes that are now landfilled will move to waste to energy. These amounts are quite significant even for the most conservative approaches as Psomopoulos et al. [41] and Yaman et al. [44] among many others have proven with their evaluations.

All these facts along with the evaluated scenarios presented here, show clearly that the energy recovery from wastes is contributing to the decarbonization of the power sector of EU, while at the same time supports the decarbonisation of other sectors such as the waste management and increases recycling. Thus, the energy recovery from wastes has a positive and not negligible role to the decarbonisation not only of the power sector of EU but covers even more sectors of economic life in their effort to decarbonisation and contributes in multiple ways.

The vast volumes of wastes in EU that are still landfilled present opportunities for further increase in energy recovery from wastes and further support of the decarbonisation efforts of EU. But these opportunities require approaches and adoption of strategies that will allow the increase the share of wastes that are used for energy recovery without threatening the goals for recycling and waste minimisation set out by EU legislation. The approaches should consider specific conditions and existing studies in each country, as well as existing facilities. A proposal from Psomopoulos [30] back in 2014, shows the advantages of using the existing lignite or coal power plants as facilities for energy recovery from wastes, and thus they can be used to increase the capacity of WTE but with significant

TABLE 4 Estimation of renewable electricity for the selected scenarios for different renewable content in waste streams

Country	50% renewable energy content in waste stream			35% renewable energy content in waste stream		
	Very optimistic	Optimistic	Basic	Very optimistic	Optimistic	Basic
	Bulgaria	440.8	339.1	203.4	308.5	237.3
Croatia	294.9	226.9	136.1	206.5	158.8	95.3
Cyprus	99.0	76.1	45.7	69.3	53.3	32.0
Czechia	612.1	470.8	282.5	428.4	329.6	197.7
Estonia	29.0	22.3	13.4	20.3	15.6	9.4
France	1884.9	1458.2	889.2	1319.4	1020.7	622.4
Greece	1090.6	838.9	503.4	763.4	587.3	352.4
Hungary	466.2	358.6	215.2	326.4	251.0	150.6
Ireland	105.3	81.0	48.6	73.7	56.7	34.0
Italy	1703.4	1326.4	823.7	1192.4	928.5	576.6
Latvia	116.4	89.5	53.7	81.5	62.7	37.6
Lithuania	80.6	62.0	37.2	56.4	43.4	26.0
Malta	67.3	51.7	31.0	47.1	36.2	21.7
Poland	1381.5	1079.8	677.5	967.0	755.8	474.2
Portugal	634.2	487.9	292.7	444.0	341.5	204.9
Romania	1075.3	827.1	496.3	752.7	579.0	347.4
Slovakia	326.0	253.4	156.7	228.2	177.4	109.7
Slovenia	27.1	21.5	14.0	19.0	15.1	9.8
Spain	3001.6	2308.9	1385.4	2101.1	1616.2	969.7
Total	13,436.1	10,380.2	6305.6	9405.3	7266.1	4413.9
United Kingdom	1512.6	1244.5	886.9	1058.8	871.1	620.9

lower investment costs, and at the same time supporting the local communities for the consequences of the EU's and MS decision to shut down these facilities under the New Green Deal in EU and the full decarbonisation of Power Sector of EU. Such approach is presenting the benefits of the existing networks (electricity and district heating in many areas) which can distribute the produced energy, as well as part of the main infrastructure that can be modified to meet the requirements and standards of WTE plants. Furthermore, the unutilised capacity of existing WTE facilities is of paramount importance. Scarlat et al. [14] showed that the existing WTE facilities in EU present an unutilised existing capacity of 31,67 thousands tonnes. This capacity exists mainly in the traditional EU Member States, with low landfilling quantities, but very close to the ones without any WTE plants, but countries like Spain and France, which present high volumes of wastes in landfills, do have unutilised capacity in the existing WTE plants. This capacity should be covered, resulting in a lower number of potential new facilities. Paramount importance for realising even the basic scenario, is the focused and case by case evaluation of the conditions in each region, along with the local plans for waste management. And here it is highly important the local communities and their opinion in WTE, as their actions supporting or against the instal-

lation and operation of a WTE can highly affect the potential realisation of such efforts.

7 | CONCLUSIONS

Waste can be used as a source of electricity, and WTE and biogas facilities are already operational in the EU. The choice of treatment processes is critical from both an economic and environmental standpoint. Wastes, waste-derived fuels such as RDF/SRF, and MSW-derived biogas production are practical options for potential energy security since they can substitute fossil fuels. Energy recovery from wastes is a promising strategy with well-established and well-proven methods for assisting the EU's energy transformation efforts. This method has major two-fold advantages: wastes are processed while energy and precious materials are recovered, allowing for even further greening of the EU economy. Energy recovery from wastes contributes significantly to efforts to decarbonize the power sector, while also offering several indirect benefits to the economy by new sources of supply, such as additional recycling and renewable fertilizers. These advantages extend beyond this stage, as waste-derived energy covers base loads with lower

grid losses and improves network security and stability. Energy recovery from waste appears to play a minor but significant role in the EU power market, with the ability and capacity to grow its share while also supporting the energy transition and circular economy in a variety of ways towards a sustainable future. The results from the estimation of the untapped potential for WTE shows that the potential contribution, especially in countries with high landfilling of wastes, is notable and can be multiplied towards low carbon communities, as the emissions are reduced even further through the reduction of carbon emissions associated to landfilling and waste management. Renewable electricity that can be recovered is significantly high and since is covering based loads can further support the stability of the electricity networks of EU, promoting also distributed generation and higher distribution efficiencies, as these power plants are closely located to end users. Basic action to utilize this potential is the operation of existing facilities in their full capacity, transforming existing coal/lignite power plants to WTE power plants, and the strategically development of new facilities, in selected areas, based on the specific plans of the countries/regions where these facilities can be installed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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